

EFFICIENCY OF USING GAMES IN BIOLOGY CLASSES

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Annotation: *The article discusses the importance of games in increasing the effectiveness of biology lessons.*

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The use of interactive methods plays an important role in the teaching of biology in the educational process on the basis of modern educational technologies. It is necessary to properly organize the learning process using an interactive method of teaching, in which the students in the classroom are fully involved in the process of learning and learning. They will have the opportunity to think freely about everything they think and know. In this process, students make their own individual contribution. Students share their thoughts, knowledge activities, worldviews and ideas related to a new topic.

The use of maps and geographical atlases is important in making biology lessons fun and exhibitions. Teaching students how to use a map and how to read it develops their ability to be interested in geographical knowledge. A student who knows how to read maps from biology can quickly learn theoretical knowledge of biology. There are also cases when students cannot find a geographical object on the map. Well what to do in this case is how the reader will quickly find the desired objects on the card. Geographical games help in this. Play is an irreplaceable organizational form of child activity. That is why the game plays an important role in the education of geoeological education.

The integrated use of play in parenting can affect a child's activities and direct him or her in different directions. That's why in the team forms of the game, the organizing kids can follow the other kids as well. This means that the play factor has a great educational value. In our opinion, from biology, the games used can be divided into five groups depending on the nature.

1. Table performance / lotto, crossword, rebuses /

2. Competition games (sharp-witted poetry, tournaments /
3. Action games
4. Role-playing games
5. Computer games

Role-playing games. In this method of teaching, students recreate 'real life' situations. This allows them to try and test new types of activities that can be applied in their practical work.

Application:

- Demonstrating the ability to try new types of activities;
- In teaching students to apply theory in practice;
- In further increasing student engagement.

Advantages:

- «realrestoration of life;
- deeper involvement of students in the topic;
- Seeing students have a different approach to the problem

allow

Group discussion: This method of teaching is based on students 'interaction and exchange of ideas. In this, the group develops a specific topic or problem based on analysis, evaluation and verification.

Application.

- Enhancing interest and thinking, in encouraging thinking;
- In strengthening lecture reading and other methods;
- In developing the main part of the training content;
- In developing the intended solution to the problem;
- When making a conclusion or inspection;
- In assessing subject comprehensibility;
- In preparing students for the next lesson.

Advantages:

- Increases interest in students and strengthens their involvement in the lesson;
- Students will have the opportunity to share ideas and experiences.

Geocological play is the most convenient tool for activating children's interest in knowledge. The most interesting of these are role-playing games, in which children with the initiative can solve the tasks set before them, overcome difficulties, influence the character of love of work.

Children get tired of dry, boring activities, and are always ready for the game.

The game can be used in geological education and has a wide range of games. Games to increase knowledge encourage students to learn more.

A game of finding without making a sound. Before starting the game, the rules of the game are explained to the students. A student who actively participates in the game and has previously fulfilled the conditions will be graded.

Game content. The teacher says the name of any geological object.

Tutorial. Students search for this object on a map and atlas.

The course of the game. When the student finds the object, he raises his right hand. Shows the teacher the object he found. The student must hold the object with his hand. Because the child next to him can see and use it. Therefore, the student who finds the object must remember the name of the place. The teacher should go to the student who found it first and raise his hand and check it.

Students who shout "I found it" or "I found it" will not be taken into account, and children will be warned about this. The student who finds the object first in the game must show it on a map or atlas. Other students are also asked to object to test how much they have learned. After the student who has found the object is seated, the teacher says the name of the new object.

Map finding game. Depending on the content of the lesson, the game will be on objects on different pages of the geographical atlas. After playing this game several times, students are asked to determine the geographical coordinates of the name they will find. To do this, the preferred students who have selected the city and nature reserves will write in a notebook the coordinates of the places found.

Geological dictionary. Game condition. This game is performed by two students and this game is judged and written by one person. In doing so, students say the geographical terms and names that begin in turn.

The course of the game. For example, if the game starts with the letter "A", it means abiotic, aspect, anthropogenic, acclimatization, aquatorium: if the game starts with the letter "b", it means biosphere, biotic, biomass. A term or name that has not been found or has nothing to do with biology is considered defeated by the reader who utters it.

What do you know about the Red Book?? The content of the game. Game participants will be asked questions on the "Red Book". "Questions are asked about the names, classes, families and families of animals and plants listed in the Red Book.

Turn off the sound. In this game, different sounds in nature are recorded on a magnetic tape and they are released. Some imitation readers may also make the voices of many animals. The sound should be repeated 2-3 times. Those who find the right one are encouraged.

This means that if the course is organized on the basis of modern technologies, it should cover all the possibilities of scientific achievements and serve the clearly defined goals that correspond to the interests and abilities of students.

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